

Agro2Circular

D7.6 – Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Draft)

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Authors: Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT)

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Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Life Cycle Assessment methodology.....	7
2.1	Life Cycle Assessment brief description	7
2.2	Carbon footprint	8
3	Plastic chain.....	9
3.1	Goal and scope.....	9
3.1.1	Goal and scope of the study	9
3.1.2	Case presentation	9
3.1.3	Calculated scenarios	11
3.1.4	Functional unit	11
3.1.5	Assumptions.....	11
3.1.6	Impact assessment method.....	12
3.2	Inventory data	12
3.3	Results	13
3.3.1	Commercial pellet.....	13
3.3.2	A2C pellet manufacturing at GWC Plastics	14
4	Agri-food chain.....	16
4.1	Goal and scope.....	16
4.1.1	Goal.....	16
4.1.2	Case presentation	16
4.1.3	Functional unit	19
4.1.4	Calculated scenarios	19
4.1.5	Assumptions.....	20
4.1.6	Benchmark products	20
4.1.7	Impact assessment method.....	22
4.2	Life Cycle Inventory	22
4.3	Results	23
4.3.1	Results for agri-food chain.....	23
4.3.2	Allocation scenario results.....	26
5	Conclusions	29
6	References	30
7	Annexes.....	31

List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
CO ₂ eq.	Carbon dioxide equivalent
EF	Environmental footprint
FU	Functional unit
CFF	Circular footprint formula
CFP	Carbon footprint of a project
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
PEF	Product environmental footprint

1 Introduction

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project will develop at laboratory scale new technologies for the upcycling of Fruits & Vegetable agri-food Wastes (F&VW) and non-renewable multilayer plastics into new high added value products with application in the food, nutraceuticals and cosmetic sectors.

To verify the environmental sustainability advantages of new technologies such as the ones developed in the A2C project, sustainability assessments such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) are needed. LCA as a method makes sure that no life cycle stage is excluded and that environmental burdens do not shift along the value chain or environmental impact categories.

This deliverable contains the preliminary estimation of the carbon footprint of two product examples in the A2C plastic (chapter 3) and agri-food chain (chapter 4). The study is a screening in which preliminary data is used to evaluate the carbon footprint. The screening approach is applied because the agri-food chain is at pre-industrial level and because the A2C territorial circular systemic solution in Murcia (hereafter referred to as Murcia demonstrator) is under development. The purpose of the deliverable is to identify already in the pilot technology development stage the main contributors (e.g. process or life cycle stage) to the carbon footprint of the A2C product chains and provide valuable feedback for the technology developers.

When the Murcia demonstrator is further developed in the A2C project, a full LCA will be carried out to address the data gaps of this screening LCA. In the full LCA the entire circular life cycle of the A2C concepts is modeled from the parts where data will be available. The use of the Circular Footprint Formula developed by European Commission (European Commission, 2021) will be evaluated to estimate for example the impact of using recycled materials. Additionally, more impact categories such as acidification, eutrophication, resource and water use will be included in the LCA depending on characteristics of the Murcia demonstrator.

2 Life Cycle Assessment methodology

In this chapter LCA method and carbon footprint calculation are presented. More detailed LCA methodology presentation is available in the Agro2Circular deliverable 7.5 *Evaluation framework and methodology*. Therefore, in this deliverable the LCA method is described briefly. Because only carbon footprint is calculated in this preliminary LCA, the carbon footprint calculation methodology is presented separately.

2.1 Life Cycle Assessment brief description

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a quantitative method for assessing the potential environmental impacts of a product or a service taking into account each life cycle stage. Typical LCA stages are production of raw materials and energy, manufacturing of the product, all transportations, distribution, use phase, and final disposal of the product or other End of Life treatment.

The LCA principles are presented in ISO 14040 and 10444 standards (ISO 14040, 2006; ISO 14044, 2006). Modelling the life cycle of a product is based on interlinked unit processes that are connected to each other with material or energy flows. Each process consists of inputs and outputs, which connect the process to previous and following processes. Besides the ISO Standards, the LCA carried out in the project will also follow the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology developed by the European Commission (European Commission, 2021). The PEF methodology aims to provide a methodology that enables measuring environmental impacts in a common way among LCA practitioners.

Life cycle assessment has four stages as shown in Figure 1: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) and interpretation of results. The LCA process is normally iterative, and some phases might need to be revised during the calculation process.

Figure 1. The four stages of life cycle assessment according to ISO 14040 (2006).

2.2 Carbon footprint

The carbon footprint calculation in this LCA follows the ISO 14076 standard Carbon footprint of products (ISO 14067, 2018). The standard provides principles, requirements and guidelines for the quantification and communication of the carbon footprint of products and services. Partial product footprints are also addressed.

Carbon footprint calculation is based on life cycle assessment using the single impact category of climate change. The quantification and reporting of a carbon footprint of a product (CFP) in accordance with this technical specification is based on the principles of the LCA (ISO 14040, 2006; ISO 14044, 2006).

The goal of a carbon footprint study of a product is to calculate the potential contribution of a product to global warming by calculating all relevant GHG emissions and removals during the product's life cycle of selected processes taking into account cut-off criteria. The carbon footprint is expressed as CO₂eq (carbon dioxide equivalent) which is a unit for comparing the radiative forcing of a GHG to that of carbon dioxide. (ISO 14067, 2018).

For each GHG a characterization factor is applied. The applied characterization factors used in this study for most common GHGs are listed in Table 1. It should be noted that the list is not complete, and all the factors are available in the dataset provided by European Commission's European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment (European Commission, 2019). The factors are according to the EF 3.0 impact assessment method from which the climate change impact category is used. The climate change is calculated using the indicator global warming potential (GWP100) over 100-year time horizon. The GWP100 is expressed in carbon dioxide equivalent.

Table 1. Characterization factors of most common greenhouse gases used in EF 3.0 impact assessment method for climate change impact category. The list does not include all the greenhouse gases. (European Commission, 2019).

Greenhouse gas	Characterization factor in EF 3.0
carbon dioxide, fossil	1
carbon monoxide, fossil	1,57
chloroform	20
dinitrogen monoxide	298
methane, fossil	36,8
methane, non-fossil	34
nitrogen fluoride	1,79

3 Plastic chain

The main aim of the A2C plastic chain is to upcycle multi-layer plastic residues from food sector to high added value products. In the A2C project the studied plastic waste streams are agriculture multi-layer disinfection mulch film waste and waste from aseptic bags produced by the food industry. This screening LCA examines only the mulch film waste as raw material of manufacturing a plastic pellet from LDPE. A pellet produced only from recycled plastic is not typically used in the industry as it is. Instead, it is normally blended with virgin plastic. Therefore, the studied product is commercial pellet which is manufactured both from recycled and virgin plastic.

In this chapter first the goal and scope of the LCA calculation is defined in chapter 3.1. Chapter 3.2 introduces the data used in the calculation. Finally, the results are presented in chapter 3.3.

3.1 Goal and scope

This subchapter includes setting the goal for LCA, description of the calculated case, definition of the functional unit and list of assumptions used in the calculation.

3.1.1 Goal and scope of the study

The goal of A2C plastic chain LCA is to evaluate the preliminary carbon footprint of producing 1 kg of commercial LDPE (low density polyethylene) pellet. The main purpose of the study at this point is to provide information for the technology partners in A2C project about the environmental hot spots of the recycled plastic production value chain.

The screening LCA compares two commercial pellets:

1. Pellet blend which is 1/3 by weight made of the recycled LDPE and virgin calcium carbonate manufactured in the A2C project (hereafter referred to as A2C pellet) and 2/3 virgin LDPE pellet
2. 100% virgin LDPE pellet

The final product was chosen to be a commercial pellet instead of the recycled A2C pellet because a pellet produced only from recycled plastic is not typically used in the industry. Virgin plastic is added to maintain the technical pellet characteristics and performance in use stage in a specific level.

3.1.2 Case presentation

The A2C plastic chain LCA flow chart is presented in the

Figure 2. The

Figure 2 also shows the stages and processes of the life cycle which are included and excluded from the assessment. The LCA is a so-called cradle-to-gate study which starts from extraction of the raw materials of the commercial pellet and ends at the gate of GWC Plastics (A2C project partner) when the A2C pellet is manufactured. Therefore, the whole life cycle of a commercial pellet is not modelled in this LCA. The results of this cradle-to-gate LCA are not as complete as the ones of a LCA where all life cycle stages are included in the evaluation. The cradle-to-gate approach was chosen for this screening study based on the data availability and the goal and scope of the study.

Figure 2. System boundary of the plastic chain LCA.

In this LCA, the main input is the mulch film waste which GWC Plastics receives. This waste includes LDPE, disinfection substances and soil. GWC Plastics carries out several steps of grinding and washing, aiming to remove as much soil and contaminants as possible from the LDPE before the pellet is manufactured. Transports marked with a truck symbol are included. Transport distances and vehicle types used in the calculation are shown in Annex E. Direct carbon dioxide emissions are released from using petrol in the A2C pellet manufacturing. The full list of process steps carried out at GWC Plastics is presented in the Annex A. To carry out the pre-treatment and pellet manufacturing, energy, calcium carbonate, water treatment chemicals and water are needed. More detailed inventory data of these inputs and outputs is available in chapter 3.2. Manufacturing the A2C pellet generates plastic filter chunk and residues which are recycled. The use of applying allocation scenarios to divide the emissions between the A2C pellet and other outputs is evaluated in the full LCA. The recycling processes of the residues are not included in this LCA, but the estimated transports to recycling centers are included. The emissions from the recycling operations are excluded due to the screening nature of the LCA. The infrastructure of the GWC Plastics plant is not included in the LCA, but in the other processes, the infrastructure is part of theecoinvent datasets.

For modelling purposes, the A2C pellet manufactured at GWC Plastics is blended together with virgin LDPE to form a final composition of pellet in use. This final product in this LCA is called commercial pellet.

The life cycle stages before and after the pellet production are excluded. The stage that occurs prior to A2C pellet manufacturing is the mulch film waste collection. This is not included because the carbon footprint of the collection process is assumed be insignificant and, can thus be excluded at this screening stage LCA. The processes which take place after the GWC Plastics plant are distribution, use and End of Life of the commercial pellet.

These stages are not taken into account because data is not easily available on them and they will be studied more in detail in the A2C final LCA.

3.1.3 Calculated scenarios

The reference product to which the A2C pellet and virgin LDPE pellet blend is compared to is a commercial pellet made 100% from virgin LDPE.

The calculated scenarios in this LCA are presented in Table 2. The scenarios are different based on the commercial pellet composition and applied electricity profile. Two electricity profiles were chosen to demonstrate the current Spanish electricity profile and possible future where all electricity is produced from renewable sources. The current Spanish electricity profile is from 2018. It should be noted that the electricity profiles of other processes than A2C pellet production and virgin pellet productions vary according to the geography of the used ecoinvent datasets listed in Annex D.

Table 2. Calculated scenarios in the A2C plastic chain LCA.

Scenario	Commercial pellet composition	Electricity profile	
		A2C pellet production	Virgin pellet production
1a	1/3 A2C pellet and 2/3 virgin LDPE pellet	Spanish average electricity and solar panels	Spanish average electricity
1b	1/3 A2C pellet and 2/3 virgin LDPE pellet	wind electricity	wind electricity
2a	100% virgin LDPE	-	Spanish average electricity
2b	100% virgin LDPE	-	wind electricity

3.1.4 Functional unit

The functional unit of the plastic chain LCA is manufacturing 1 kg of commercial LDPE pellet.

3.1.5 Assumptions

The following assumptions are applied in this A2C plastic LCA:

Related to A2C pellet manufacturing:

- The mulch film waste which is the main raw material of the A2C pellet is considered as emission free because it is recycled
- Calcium carbonate is manufactured in Spain and average Spanish electricity profile is used in the production
- Polyelectrolyte chemical and calcium oxide are transported 150 km. This estimation is added for modeling purposes and based on value inserted by VTT to represent a transport of relative short distance.
- Waste resulting from GWC Plastics operations (soil, plastic sawdust and filter chunk) are recycled

- Only carbon dioxide emissions come from using the petrol. Other emissions such as NO_x and SO_x are not taken into account in this LCA because the beforementioned emissions do not contribute to carbon footprint.
- The technical characteristics of the recycled pellet (strength, needed amount etc.) is the same as virgin LDPE pellet
- A commercial LDPE pellet includes 1/3 of recycled LDPE

Related to virgin LDPE:

- The virgin pellet LCI data is available for granulate. The granulate has the same characteristics as pellet.

3.1.6 Impact assessment method

The results of the A2C plastic chain screening LCA are calculated using Environmental Footprint EF3.0 carbon footprint method (European Commission, 2019). The LCA is carried out using Sulca software¹ developed by VTT.

3.2 Inventory data

The data used in the plastic chain LCA model is presented in the Table 3. The main data is provided by A2C partner GWC Plastics and represents a period of two months. The data is industrial scale and is valid for both multi-layer and mono-material mulch film waste. VTT calculated the direct carbon dioxide emission of using the petrol based on the carbon content of the petrol. List of the chosen LCA database ecoinvent processes is available in Annex D in Table 7.

Table 3. Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic chain screening LCA for A2C pellet manufacturing. Values are calculated per functional unit.

INPUTS			
Name	Amount	Unit	Source
agricultural mulch film waste	0,6282	kg	GWC Plastics
calcium carbonate	0,01	kg	
polyelectrolyte chemical for water treatment	1,79E-04	kg	
calcium oxide	2,23E-03	kg	
water	0,1208	kg	
electricity	0,3635	kWh	
electricity from solar panel	0,03366	kWh	
petrol	6,43E-04	kg	
OUTPUTS			
Name	Amount	Unit	Source
A2C pellet	0,3333	kg	GWC Plastics
soil	0,22	kg	
plastic sawdust	0,08	kg	
carbon dioxide to air	2,04E-03	kg	VTT calculation

¹ <https://www.simulationstore.com/sulca5>

As described in the previous chapter, the final product is a pellet which is a mix of A2C recycled plastic pellet and virgin LDPE pellet. Table 4 demonstrates the composition of such pellet and the composition of the reference product in the studied scenarios.

Table 4. Final composition of the modelled commercial pellets per functional unit in the studied scenarios.

Scenario	Plastic type	Amount	Unit
1a and 1b (A2C case)	A2C pellet	0,333	kg
	Virgin LDPE pellet	0,667	kg
2a and 2b (reference case)	Virgin LDPE pellet	1	kg

3.3 Results

The results presented in this chapter are preliminary and aim to indicate the early priority technology development needs from carbon footprint point of view for the A2C plastic chain technologies. The screening LCA results shown in this chapter serve as important feedback to the A2C developers early in the project to detect the preliminary main sources of GHG emissions.

3.3.1 Commercial pellet

Figure 3 shows the results of the A2C plastic chain screening LCA. As the result of scenario 1a shows, the carbon footprint of the commercial pellet with 1/3 of recycled material, is currently 1,4 kgCO₂eq/1 kg of commercial pellet. In the future (scenario 1b), the carbon footprint when renewable electricity is available, is estimated to be 1,1 kgCO₂eq/1 kg of commercial pellet.

Similarly, the carbon footprint of the reference product from purely virgin raw material is currently 1,9 kgCO₂eq/1 kg of commercial pellet (scenario 2a) and in the future 1,6 kgCO₂eq/1 kg of commercial pellet (scenario 2b).

Figure 3. Results of the A2C plastic chain screening LCA.

Three main observations can be noticed from the results.

First, when comparing the scenarios with average Spanish electricity (1a and 2a), it can be seen that using A2C pellet as part of a commercial pellet instead of 100% virgin pellet, reduces the commercial pellet's carbon footprint by 26%.

Second, it can be noted by examining the results of scenario 1a that great majority of the blended commercial pellet's current carbon footprint is created by the virgin LDPE's life cycle stages. More specifically, the production of virgin ethylene comprises 72% of the total carbon footprint of scenario 1a. Manufacturing the recycled pellet emits significantly less GHG emissions because the raw material, mulch film waste, is considered to be emission free as explained in chapter 3.1.5. On the contrary, the main raw material of the virgin LDPE, ethylene, is manufactured by heating a fossil feedstock.

Third, when comparing scenario 1b to scenario 1a, it can be seen that using only renewable electricity in the A2C and virgin pellet manufacturing decreases the footprint of a commercial blended pellet by 21%. The decrease is not that drastic, because the production of the virgin ethylene, in which the use of renewable energy is not included, remains to be the main contributor to the commercial pellet's carbon footprint in scenario 1b.

3.3.2 A2C pellet manufacturing at GWC Plastics

In this subchapter, the results are shown only from operations which take place in the manufacturing of the A2C pellet at GWC Plastics. These operations are energy consumed at GWC Plastics, chemicals, added water and A2C pellet production's direct emissions. Therefore, the production of virgin LDPE is not included. However, the results are still

calculated per 1 kg of commercial pellet. The results offer a view to see where GWC Plastics could make improvements to reduce the carbon footprint when producing the A2C pellet.

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. shows only the carbon footprint of A2C pellet manufactured at GWC Plastics which constitutes 33 % of the commercial pellet’s weight. The values are calculated for the current Spanish electricity profile and future scenario where solely renewable electricity, wind electricity in particular, is applied.

Figure 4. Carbon footprint of manufacturing A2C pellet at GWC Plastics per different processes.

From **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** it can be observed that in scenario 1a, which represents the current A2C pellet production, consuming energy (electricity and petrol) at GWC Plastics comprises 87% of the total carbon footprint of A2C pellet. The energy consumption emissions come mainly from using the Spanish average electricity which represent 98% of the energy emissions. The production of the chemicals (calcium carbonate, CaO and polyacrylamide) cover 5% of the A2C pellet’s emissions.

When comparing the scenario 1b to scenario 1a, it can be noted that using wind electricity in the A2C pellet manufacturing could reduce the A2C pellet’s total carbon footprint by 80%. This reduction is explained by the significant impact of the electricity consumption in the A2C pellet’s carbon footprint.

4 Agri-food chain

The agri-food case is focused on utilizing waste streams from agri-food sector, e.g., apple, broccoli, cauliflower, grape, lemon and artichoke. Agri-food wastes are used for their high value bioactive compounds, to produce new foods, nutraceuticals and cosmetics. At this phase of the project, possibilities of lemon waste are investigated, and in this report the screening LCA for lemon processing is presented. In this chapter first the goal and scope of the LCA calculation is defined in chapter 4.1. Chapter 4.2 introduces the data used in the calculation. Finally, the results are presented in chapter 4.3.

4.1 Goal and scope

This subchapter includes setting the goal for LCA, description of the calculated case, definition of the functional unit and list of assumptions used in the calculation.

4.1.1 Goal

The goal of A2C agri-food chain LCA is to evaluate the preliminary carbon footprint of producing dehydrated solid and liquid extracts from lemon agri-food waste stream. The main purpose of the study at this point is to provide information for the technology partners in A2C project about the environmental hot spots of the lemon waste streams value chain.

The LCA considers 50 kg of lemon residues that are produced into two products, dehydrated solid extract / fiber extract (3,6 kg) and dehydrated liquid extract/ phenolic extract (0,6 kg). Both products are solid and air-dry. This means that also the extract derived from the liquid phase is totally dehydrated extract (moisture contents <1,5%) and its appearance is that of a powder.

The screening LCA calculations for extract are performed for two different electricity scenarios, average Spanish electricity mix and 100% renewable electricity. Produced extracts are compared to existing products or compounds, that are used as benchmarks.

4.1.2 Case presentation

The used citrus fruit agri-food waste is lemon, that consist of a white and yellow solid with high moisture content, corresponding to peel and pulp. The waste is generated from fruit juice processing and vegetable canning companies, like Citromil. The two main lemon waste types, from different stages are a) peel at the juice extraction (squeezing) stage, and b) pulp at the pulp decrease stage.

Lemon production in Spain is around 940.000 tonnes/year, and the region of Murcia accounts for more than 58% of total production. Lemon production generates a waste volume of approximately 50–55% of the processed lemon volume. Hence, in the area of Murcia, 150.000–200.000 tonnes of lemon waste is generated annually. The Citromil company working in the field generated about 4.000–4.500 tonnes/year of pulp and 30.000–40.000 tonnes/year of peel. Lemons are collected normally all year round, and the waste is constantly available. (A2C Deliverable 1.2.)

The agri-food wastes (fruits and vegetables) have high value bioactive compounds (phenolic compounds and dietary fiber), that can be retained through valorization, e.g. green

extraction, purification and stabilization. The goal is to achieve high extraction yield and high purity bioactives with high stability for new foods, nutraceuticals and cosmetics. (A2C Deliverable 2.1)

The enzymatic extraction and processing of lemon agri-food waste starts from a tank, where enzymes and water are added to the lemon waste. In the tank, the slurry is stirred with electricity and heated with natural gas into smoother mixture. Once the enzymatic extraction of compounds of interest has taken place, the temperature is increased to inactivate the enzymes. Mixture is filtrated, and the solid (~20%) and liquid (~80%) phases are separated. Solid extract, rich in fiber, goes to oven, where the mass is heated and excess water is evaporated. The output product is dehydrated solid extract, called fiber extract. The separated liquid extract, with a higher content of antioxidant and phenolic compounds, goes first into concentration, where liquid is heated, and excess water is condensed. Condensed water goes to wastewater treatment. The concentrated liquid extract proceeds to lyophilization, where it is freeze dried into dehydrated extract, called phenolic extract, which takes the form of powder. The production chain of enzymatic extraction is presented by each process in the Figure 5 below. The figure is an edited version of the process figure provided by CTNC, which is presented in Annex B Annex B.

Figure 5. Production chain of enzymatic extraction.

The system boundary shows the stages and processes of the life cycle included and excluded from the assessment. Like in the previously presented plastic LCA, this is a cradle-to-gate study which starts from extraction of the raw materials of the lemon extracts and ends at the CTNC gate producing the extracts. Cradle to gate approach was chosen based on the goal and scope of the study, as explained in plastic chain chapter 3.1.2. The goal of the process is to provide information for technology partners to refine the processes, and therefore the user phase is not in the center of interest in the project. Therefore, the whole life cycle of dehydrated extracts are not modelled in this LCA, and user aspect is excluded.

The phases of the production chain are used in the LCA modelling and are simplified for Figure 6 below. The system boundaries of the agri-food waste are also presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. System boundaries of the agri-food waste LCA.

Direct carbon dioxide emissions are released from using natural gas. Transportations of raw materials, e.g., agri-food and enzymes, to the enzymatic extraction of lemon are excluded. Only transportations already included in the used datasets are considered, from the market values which have average transportations e.g., inside enzyme production.

The concentration phase for liquid extract production uses an auxiliary cooling agent, which is cut-off from calculations. The cooling agent is glycol water mixture consisting of 90% water and 10% propylene glycol, total amount being 100 kg. This amount is circulating and can be used for other processes using the same machinery. Glycol water is not part of the product nor in contact with the enzymatic products.

4.1.3 Functional unit

For the first scenario with the system expansion approach, the functional unit of the agri-food LCA is manufacturing

1. 3,6 kg of dehydrated solid extract / fiber extract
2. 0,6 kg of dehydrated liquid extract / phenolic extract.

The generated amount is generated from 50 kg of lemon residues.

In the allocation scenario the same functional unit is used, production of 3,6 kg fiber extract and 0,6 kg phenolic extract. To make comparison to the benchmark fiber, the allocated production of fiber extract is also converted for 1 kg of fiber extract produced separately.

4.1.4 Calculated scenarios

Since the lemon waste processing has two output products, the concept is considered in two ways (called scenarios). Since there are some processing steps that include both product streams (tank and filtration), the burden from these steps needs to be allocated to both products, if the products want to be considered separately. However, since the ISO 14040-44 (2006) standards recommend to avoid allocation, the first scenario considers the process with both products in the functional unit, i.e. the concept is considered with system expansion and includes both the solid and liquid extract production.

For the first scenario (system expansion i.e. both products), two possibilities for the enzymatic extraction's electricity use are studied:

- 1a Spanish average electricity mix for year 2018
- 1b 100% wind electricity from Spain

To be able to calculate the carbon footprint for each product separately, scenario 2 is an allocation scenario, based on dry mass allocation. Dry mass allocation is done based on the information given by CTNC, which is presented in Annex B. The dry mass of the solid phase, fiber extract product is calculated to be 75% of the total input of the process. Accordingly, the dry mass of dehydrated liquid phase, phenolic extract is calculated to be 25% of the total dry mass. The total impact of the processes where total mass is processed, i.e. the first phases: tank and filtration, is divided based on these shares (75% and 25%). The total impact of the fiber extract production is therefore 75% of the tank and filtration, and 100% of the oven. Total impact of phenolic extract is 25% of the tank and filtration, and 100% of the concentration and lyophilization.

The allocation is done for both electricity scenarios using the same dry mass allocation. Allocation scenario 2a uses the Spanish average electricity mix and 2b the wind electricity.

Later in this project, a sensitivity analysis is done for this allocation scenario. Also, if the allocation would be done based on mass of final products (3,6 kg and 0,6 kg), this would give different shares for the products. In the case of mass-based allocation, water would be also included, which is considered insignificant in this process. In the case of economic

allocation, the final products' shares of impacts would be defined by the monetary values of the products. This may be studied in the later stage of the project.

4.1.5 Assumptions

The following assumptions are applied in this A2C agri-food LCA:

- Dehydrated extracts are manufactured in Spain and for electricity an average Spanish electricity profile or 100% wind power is used in the production.
- Lemon production in Spain- dataset is used for the modelling of raw material acquisition, which includes the emissions from cultivating lemons. This is assumed to represent an approximate of the climate impacts of also lemon residues. Lemon waste stream could be also regarded as emissions-free and might be excluded later. Other options (e.g. allocation) for the raw material upstream are considered at the later stage of the project.
- Transportations of raw materials, enzymes and lemon residues, are not included in the calculations at this point.
- The condensed water from concentration phase is managed as wastewater.
- The evaporated water from drying the extracts is considered as water to air.
- Carbon dioxide emissions from using the natural gas in the tank are calculated based on carbon content and carbon allocation of natural gas, gained from ecoinvent database. Other emissions such as NO_x and SO_x are not taken into account in this LCA because the aforementioned emissions do not contribute to carbon footprint.
- The auxiliary cooling agent, propylene glycol, is cut-off from calculations, when it is circulating in the system and not in contact with the product.

4.1.6 Benchmark products

When comparative products are searched for, some general features about the extracts are asked from CTNC, the producer of enzymatic extracts. The solid extracts manufactured from lemon waste streams are regarded as nutritional fibers, and therefore other nutritional fibers available in the industry are considered comparative. Explained by CTNC:

“One of the most commonly used soluble fibers is inulin. There are also other fibers that have more water retention capacity, and therefore affect the texture of the final product, e.g. oat fiber, guar gum fiber, pectin and bamboo fiber. On the other hand, there are more traditional insoluble fibers, that are used more for baking, e.g. wheat, rye, oats etc.” (Sofía Martínez (CTNC), personal communication, February 6, 2023.)

Therefore, nutritional fibers, primarily LCA results for inulin production, are searched from literature.

Comparative product for nutritional fiber, the dehydrated solid extract, is inulin produced from root chicory. Root chicory is defined as an herbaceous plant with a fleshy taproot, and it is the main source of inulin. Inulin is a prebiotic dietary fiber e.g., boosting the growth of beneficial gut bacteria and stimulating the human immune system. In the study of Hingsamer

et al. (2022) two new plant breeding technologies (NPBT) are analyzed and compared to commercial inulin production from chicory. One studied scenario aims to optimize inulin yield, and another explores the potential for multipurpose use as yielding inulin and health beneficial terpenes. Three GWP impacts are calculated for one ton of produced inulin. These calculations are also done according to cradle-to-gate approach, which makes the values comparable to this case study. The reference inulin process used in the study (Hingsamer et al. 2022) has an impact of 1,46-1,62 t CO₂ eq. The improved inulin process evaluated in the study causes an impact of 1,30-1,44 t CO₂ eq. and the multi-product process is calculated to have an impact of 1,26-1,39 t CO₂ eq. The data on the background of these LCA calculations is gathered mainly from ecoinvent 3.7.1 database, whereas calculations in this case are based on ecoinvent 3.8 database. An average of the three above-mentioned scenarios is used as a benchmark for nutritional fiber, and it is calculated to be 1,41 t CO₂ eq/ t inulin, converting the unit to kg CO₂ eq/ kg inulin. (Hingsamer et al. 2022.)

According to CTNC, produced dehydrated liquid extract, phenolic extract:

“is an extract rich in antioxidant compounds, e.g. polyphenols, flavonoids. At the moment there are no reference product, since there is no detailed information available about the nutritional features of polyphenols or antioxidant capacities. Although on the labelling there can be stated that the product contains antioxidants or polyphenols if you indicate their content in the nutritional values. These types of compounds are used in food supplement, nutraceuticals, etc, for example tocopherols, resveratrol, etc.” (Sofía Martínez (CTNC), personal communication, February 10, 2023.)

When searching for a benchmark product, the antioxidant-rich extracts are looked for.

Many possible comparative products for phenolic extract are found from literature. These products and extracts all differ from each other and their comparability with the case study (lemon-based phenolic extract) is still uncertain e.g., considering their functionality. Four potential extracts rich in different antioxidants are studied and findings are presented shortly in the Table 5 below. First product is an antioxidant-rich powder extract from beet wastes that is on laboratory scale (Arias et al. 2022). Second one is antioxidant extracted from olive mill wastewater (Kalogerakis et al. 2013). Third one is corn-based starch aerogel which contains vitamin E, also known as α -tocopherol (De Marco et al. 2019). Fourth benchmark is production of C-vitamin (ascorbic acid) antioxidant, whose information is gained from the ecoinvent 3.8 database.

Table 5. Potential benchmark products for phenolic extract.

Benchmark product:	More information:	Scale:	GWP impact	Converted GWP impact [kg CO ₂ eq./kg]	Source:
Antioxidant-rich powder extract from beet wastes	Ten different scenarios using beet root and leaf residues as inputs and five different extraction techniques. Used reference is pressurized	Laboratory	0,06 kg CO ₂ eq./ 1 g extract	60	Arias et al. 2022

	liquid extraction (PLE) on beet leaves, for 1 g.				
Antioxidants from olive mill wastewater (OMW)	Three polyphenolic compounds recovered with liquid-liquid solvent extraction (three different solvents tested). Used reference is hydroxytyrosol extraction (0,247 kg from 1 m ³ OMW) with ethyl acetate solvent.	Laboratory	13,3 kg CO ₂ eq. / g hydroxytyrosol	13.300	Kalogerakis et al. 2013
Starch aerogel tablets containing vitamin E	Corn-based starch, aerogel preparation using supercritical carbon dioxide impregnation. Used reference the vitamin E (α -tocopherol, TOC) amount (15 mg) in a tablet (120 mg).	Industrial	2,53 -02 kg CO ₂ eq. / 15 mg vitamin E	1687	De Marco et al. 2019
C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	Dataset name: "ascorbic acid production", location RER. LCIA results, EF v3.0.	Industrial	2,9093 kg CO ₂ eq. / kg	2,9093	ecoinvent 3.8 database

The GWP impacts of the benchmark products for phenolic extract presented in Table 5 are very different when converted to the same unit. Results for different antioxidant products vary from 2,9 to 13.300 kg of CO₂ eq./ kg product. Because of this great variety, one single benchmark cannot be chosen at this point of the project. The functionality of produced lemon waste phenolic extract is not clear, and there are no definitions of what antioxidants could be replaced with the phenolic extract product. The functionality and other features of phenolic extract will be more thoroughly assessed further in the project, to estimate how comparable these benchmarks are to it.

The potential of other benchmark products for both fiber and phenolic extract will be studied in the full LCA later in the project, and their suitability will be examined in more detail.

4.1.7 Impact assessment method

The results of the A2C agri-food screening LCA are calculated using Environmental Footprint EF3.0 carbon footprint method (European Commission, 2019). The LCA calculations were done with Sulca software developed by VTT, and the flowsheet of Sulca can be seen in Annex C.

4.2 Life Cycle Inventory

The data used in the agri-food LCA model is presented in Table 6. The main data is provided by A2C partner CTNC. The data provided is pilot scale. VTT calculated the direct carbon dioxide emission of using the natural gas based on the carbon content of the natural gas. The evaporated water from heating or drying the products (in tank, oven and lyophilization) was calculated based

on the mass balance in the process. List of the chosen LCA database ecoinvent processes is available in Annex D in

Table 8.

Table 6. Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic chain screening LCA for A2C pellet manufacturing. Values are calculated per functional unit.

INPUTS			
Name	Amount	Unit	Source
agri-food waste (lemon)	50	kg	CTNC
enzyme	0,005	kg	
water (boiler feed water)	0,19	m ³	
water (for extraction)	0,15	m ³	
electricity	320,4	kWh	
natural gas	6	m ³	
OUTPUTS			
Name	Amount	Unit	Source
dehydrated solid extract	3,6	kg	CTNC
dehydrated liquid extract	0,6	kg	
condensed water	0,08	m ³	
carbon dioxide to air	11,13	kg	VTT calculation
evaporated water	305,8	kg	VTT calculation

4.3 Results

The results presented in this chapter are preliminary and aim to indicate the early priority technology development needs from carbon footprint point of view for the agri-food chain technologies. The screening LCA results shown in this chapter serve as important feedback to the A2C developers early in the project to detect the preliminary main sources of GHG emissions.

The results are calculated for producing the functional unit (FU) of extracts (3,6 kg and 0,6 kg) with two previously presented energy scenarios 1a and 1b. Results for the dry mass allocation are calculated for both energy scenarios (2a & 2b). Allocation results are also used for calculating the emissions caused by 1 kg of each extract, and to compare the nutritional fiber extracts to the chosen benchmark fiber.

4.3.1 Results for agri-food chain

The results are calculated for the two electricity scenarios (1a: Spanish electricity mix and 1b: Wind electricity), separated by the main processes and the stages of production. The results of the energy scenarios comparing 1a and 1b and separated by the main processes are presented in the Figure 7 below.

Carbon footprint of producing 3,6 kg nutritional fiber and 0,6 kg phenolic extract, in two energy scenarios by the main processes

Figure 7. Carbon footprint of producing 3,6 kg nutritional fiber and 0,6 kg phenolic extract, in two energy scenarios by the main processes.

From the Figure 7 above, it can be seen that changing the electricity into 100% renewable cuts the carbon footprint by 77%. This reduction is mainly gained from the energy sectors cut emissions. The remaining emissions caused by energy are the direct emissions caused by the use of natural gas in the tank. Cutting the use of fossil fuels as natural gas would lower the energy emissions even more. The chemicals used in the process, enzymes, are currently not visible in the table, mainly caused by the small quantity used (5 grams per 50 kg lemon residues). The impact of wastewater treatment is minimal in both scenarios. The impact of raw materials, currently calculated with lemon production and marked with striped grey, is now included in the calculations. Lemon production impacts could also be excluded when lemon is not produced for this purpose and is waste steam.

The process of producing 3,6 kg of nutritional fiber and 0,6 kg of phenolic extract has many sub-processes, known as the stages of production. The emissions of producing the extracts in two energy scenarios, separated by the stages of production, are presented in the Figure 8 below.

Figure 8. Carbon footprint of producing 3,6 kg nutritional fiber and 0,6 kg phenolic extract, in two energy scenarios by the stages of production.

When separating results by the stages of production, as in the Figure 8 above, the lyophilization, freeze-drying, has the biggest impact on the carbon footprint because of the high energy consumption in the process in scenario 1a. The tank production stage shows similar results in both scenarios 1a, which can be explained by the source of emissions in the processes being other than electricity. In the tank, most of the emissions are caused by the use of natural gas (c. 70%) and raw materials (lemon production) (c. 30%). It should be noted, as stated before, that the emissions caused by the lemon production could be ignored as well. The impacts of oven and concentration stages are similar in scenario 1a, in both where the emissions are mostly caused by the energy consumption.

In the scenario 1b, where the emissions are decreased to one third compared to scenario 1a, the emissions are decreased especially from the most electricity consuming processes. In scenario 1b the most impact on carbon footprint is caused by the processes in the tank. Therefore, in scenario 1b the most influential processes are the ones where electricity-use is not the main source of emissions, as the previously mentioned tank where natural gas and lemon production are included. If electricity profile is transferred to a more renewable option, the remaining processes to focus interest is the use of natural gas. The lemon production could be excluded from the tank stage, since the used lemon is a waste fraction of which emissions could be ignored. Emissions caused by the use of natural gas could be cut with reconsidering the use of fuels and investigating possibilities to use other non-fossil fuels.

4.3.2 Allocation scenario results

The allocation scenario is calculated for both energy scenarios, called allocation scenarios 2a and 2b. All results are calculated for producing 3,6 kg of nutritional fiber and 0,6 kg of phenolic extract. The allocation is used for the stages of production where both solid and liquid phases are present: tank and filtration. In those processes, 75% of emissions are allocated to the solid phase and 25% to the liquid phase. Emissions from oven are allocated for the solid phase, and emissions from concentration and lyophilization are allocated to the liquid phase.

The allocation scenario 2a using average Spanish electricity mix is presented first. In the Figure 9 below the allocated results for the scenario 2a are presented separately for solid and liquid phases, with color codes indicating the stages of production.

Figure 9. Allocated carbon footprint of solid and liquid phases produced with Spanish electricity mix, by the stages of production.

As from the Figure 9 above can be seen, the production of 3,6 kg nutritional fiber, the solid phase causes emissions of circa 30 kg CO₂ eq. Solid phases emissions consist mainly of the tank and oven, where raw material (lemon production), natural gas and energy are the main sources of emissions. As discussed before, the emissions from lemon production (c. 6 kg of total production) could be ignored, and emissions from solid and liquid phases decreased according to allocated shares, in solid phase c. 4,5 kg and in liquid phase c. 1,5 kg. The liquid phase, and production of 0,6 kg phenolic extract causes multifold emissions, c. 95 kg CO₂ eq. Bigger emissions of the liquid phase are caused mainly from the freeze drying in the lyophilization, which uses a lot of energy. Some emissions are also caused by the energy use in the concentration phase and oven.

In this screening LCA study, the allocation results are shown only for the production stages. Breakdown of the results in the main processes (raw materials, production of consumed energy etc.) are presented in the full LCA deliverable when the final allocation method is defined.

Next the allocation scenario 2b using wind electricity is presented. In the Figure 10 the allocated results for the scenario 2b are presented separately for solid and liquid phases, with color codes indicating the stages of production.

Figure 10. Allocated carbon footprint of solid and liquid phases produced with wind electricity, by the stages of production.

From the above Figure 10 it can be seen that with 100% renewable energy the difference between solid and liquid extracts production is smaller than in scenario 2a. In scenario 2b the solid phase and production of 3,6 nutritional fiber causes circa 16 kg CO₂ eq., while liquid phase and production of 0,6 kg phenolic extract causes circa 12 kg CO₂ eq. When energy source is changed from electricity mix to renewable energy, the emissions from the liquid phase decrease more. Liquid phase emissions drop from c. 95 kg to 12 kg, whereas solid phase is halved from c. 30 kg to 16 kg. The greater decrease in liquid phase emissions is explained with the most influential process in production, lyophilization, of which emissions are mostly caused from the use of electricity.

The production of nutritional fiber can be compared to the chosen benchmark extract, the inulin fiber reported by Hingsamer et al. (2022) as described in chapter 4.1.6. Phenolic extract, the dehydrated liquid phase, is not compared to any benchmark since there is no defined benchmark for phenolic extract at this point.

In this section, the emissions of inulin fiber are compared to the dry mass allocated emissions of nutritional fiber. These allocated values are transferred for one kilogram of product instead of previous 3,6 kg, to make the values comparable. In the scenario 2a the emissions caused by solid phase is circa 30 kg CO₂ eq., which divided by 3,6 kg leaves emissions of c. 8 kg CO₂ eq./ 1 kg nutritional fiber. In the scenario 2b, the emissions caused by solid phase are in total c. 16 kg CO₂ eq., which divided by 3,6 kg leaves 4,5 kg CO₂ eq./ 1 kg of nutritional fiber. In the Figure 11 below the allocated production of 1 kg nutritional fiber in two energy scenarios is compared to the benchmark product inulin.

Figure 11. Allocated production of 1 kg nutritional fiber: lemon waste fiber with two energy scenarios compared to benchmark fiber.

As the Figure 11 above shows, the emissions for nutritional fiber from lemon waste are higher in both energy scenarios compared to the inulin fiber's emissions. The carbon footprint of A2C fiber produced with renewable energy is three-folded compared to inulin, and the average electricity mix produced A2C fiber is almost six-folded. However, the allocation results compared to benchmark are approximated, based on preliminary screening LCA. It must be remembered that the lemon processing data was on a pilot level while the inulin production is on industrial level. It can be expected that energy consumption of the pilot data can be remarkably decreased when the processing of the lemon waste would be on industrial level. The comparability to the benchmark product(s) will be further considered in a later stage of the project.

5 Conclusions

The conclusions presented in this chapter are preliminary and formed based on an early screening LCA. A more thorough LCA that takes also into account the circularity of the A2C plastic and agri-food chains will be carried out later in the A2C project. Meanwhile, the results and conclusions from this screening LCA serve as material to detect the possible carbon footprint hotspots and evaluate the preliminary carbon footprint of the A2C plastic and agri-food extraction technologies.

From the plastic chain results it can be concluded that using A2C plastic pellet as part (33% of the total commercial weight) of a commercial pellet instead of 100% virgin pellet can reduce the commercial pellet's carbon footprint by 26%. Therefore, it is recommended to maximise the share of recycled plastic in a pellet. The customers of a commercial pellet should consider if it is necessary to utilize primary plastic or could a recycled plastic be an alternative.

Although the contribution of the A2C pellet to the total carbon footprint of a commercial pellet is minor, improving energy efficiency and using renewable electricity reduces significantly the carbon footprint of manufacturing the recycled A2C plastic pellet.

In the agri-food chain the screening LCA results are calculated for producing 3,6 kg fiber extract and 0,6 kg phenolic extract. Energy use is the biggest impact source in production of the extracts, while the most energy-demanding process is lyophilization. As in the A2C plastic pellet, the total carbon footprint of agri-food chain is minimized when renewable electricity is used in the manufacturing process, because energy is the biggest contributor in carbon footprint.

In dry mass allocation the impact of fiber extract and phenolic extract are calculated based on the share of dry mass percentage in the final products. 75% of dry mass is calculated to be in solid phase and 25% in liquid phase, meaning the impacts of processes common for both extracts were divided according to these percentages. To compare lemon-based fiber to the chosen benchmark of nutritional fiber extract, the allocation results are calculated for 1 kg of fiber extract. When compared to the chosen benchmark fiber inulin, the A2C fiber extract shows to have higher carbon footprint (three to six-fold). These results are gained from preliminary screening and the suitability and comparability of the benchmark products will be assessed in future stages of this project.

In the full LCA the data gaps of this screening LCA will be addressed. For example, the whole A2C Murcia demonstrator will be modelled taking into account e.g. the emissions from using recycled materials. The use of the Circular Footprint Formula developed by European Commission (European Commission, 2021) will be evaluated for this purpose. Additionally, more impact categories such as acidification, eutrophication, resource and water use will be included in the LCA depending on characteristics of the Murcia demonstrator.

6 References

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7 Annexes

Annex A A2C pellet manufacturing steps at GWC Plastics

Figure 12. Plastic pre-treatment and preliminary decontamination system implemented by GWC for the disinfection agricultural multilayer film waste (Agro2Circular D3.9).

Annex B Enzymatic extraction process at CTNC

Figure 13. Enzymatic extraction process flow chart provided by CTNC.

Annex C Sulca flowsheet of enzymatic extraction

Figure 14. Sulca-model of the lemon waste enzymatic extraction. Colour-codes in the first box for the stages of production, and below for the main processes.

Annex D Used ecoinvent processes

Table 7. Used Ecoinvent v3.8 processes in the A2C plastic chain screening LCA.

Data	Name in Ecoinvent	Geography	Reference flow
calcium carbonate	calcium carbonate production, precipitated	RER	calcium carbonate, precipitated [kg]
calcium oxide	market for quicklime, milled, packed	RER	quicklime, milled, packed [kg]
electricity (average Spanish electricity)	market for electricity, medium voltage	ES	electricity, medium voltage [kWh]
electricity from solar panel	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted	ES	electricity, low voltage [kWh]
petrol	market for petrol, low-sulfur	Europe without Switzerland	petrol, low-sulfur [kg]
polyelectrolyte chemical for water treatment	market for polyacrylamide	GLO	polyacrylamide [kg]
virgin LDPE	polyethylene production, low density, granulate	RER	polyethylene, low density, granulate [kg]
water	market for tap water	Europe without Switzerland	tap water [kg]
wind electricity	electricity production, wind, >3MW turbine, onshore	ES	electricity, high voltage [kWh]

Table 8. Used Ecoinvent v3.8 processes in the A2C agri-food chain screening LCA.

Data	Name in Ecoinvent	Geography	Reference flow
agri-food waste (lemon)	lemon production	ES	lemon [kg]
enzyme	market for enzymes	GLO	enzymes [kg]
water	water unspecified		
electricity (average Spanish electricity)	market for electricity, medium voltage	ES	electricity, medium voltage [kWh]
wind electricity	electricity production, wind, >3MW turbine, onshore	ES	electricity, high voltage [kWh]
condensed water	market for wastewater, average	Europe without Switzerland	wastewater, average [m3]

Annex E Transport distances in the plastic chain

Table 9. Transport

Data	Transport distance (km)	Vehicle in Ecoinvent v3.8
calcium carbonate	120	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6
calcium oxide	150	
mulch film waste	60	
petrol	50	
plastic sawdust to water treatment	94	
polyelectrolyte chemical for water treatment	150	
soil waste to treatment	40	

